

LEARNING AND IMPROVING ENGLISH BY READING NOVELS, AS AN EXAMPLE OF “GONE WITH THE WIND” BY MARGARET MITCHELL

Fotima Matmusayeva

English language teacher of Kokand University

Annotation: As a language teacher, I am always in search of good books and interesting materials to enhance on my skills as well as my university students`. I found such a book that took all of my attention, worth reading and learning a lot. Margaret Mitchell’s wonderful historical epic “Gone with the Wind”, which won a Pulitzer Prize, is a remarkable tale of love and loss, patriotism, fight of old and new, strong family bonds, grace and nobility, nation mortally divided and people forever changed. Principally, it is the story of gorgeous, ruthless Scarlett O’Hara and the flamboyant soldier of prosperity, Rhett Butler.

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America’s most beloved epic novel. A month before, this indication left me in amazement and in utmost curiosity when I was searching something to read on my phone to push away my boredom at the queue at dentist’s. I started reading. From the very first pages, the book grabbed my attention on very high levels so I could not put it down. I am going to describe my viewpoints while I was reading this novel and analyze it from different perspectives, such as time and place, characters, events, relationships and etc.

“Gone with the Wind” has been boundless practice for me in the following spheres:

- It widened my horizons on American history in 1860s, culture, values, standards, morals and ethics, policy, atmosphere, social life of those times.

- I gained the chance of developing my English, particularly my vocabulary is tremendously enriched while I was unconsciously living with the characters, especially, Scarlett O`hara and entire community circled around her.
- The novel made me think one more time in my life: What is important in life in one`s whole lifetime.
- I was motivated by courageous some principles of characters, such as not giving up no matter what happens, unconditional love to motherland, loving and caring about family and relatives and close people, being brave, faithfulness, dignity and hope for tomorrow.

Main characters of the novel are Scarlett O`hara, Rhett Butler, Gerald O`hara, Miss Ellen, Mammy, Ashley Wilkes, Melanie Hamilton, Suellen, Cathleen (the two are Scarlet`s younger sisters), Charles Hamilton, Frank Kennedy, Tarleton family, Will Benteen, Dr. Meade, India, Miss Meriwether,

Scarlett O`hara is described as in her face were too sharply blended the delicate features of her mother, a Coast aristocrat of French descent, and the heavy ones of her florid Irish father. But it was an arresting face, pointed of chin, square of jaw. Her eyes were pale green without a touch of hazel, starred with bristly black lashes and slightly tilted at the ends. Above them, her thick black brows slanted upward, cutting a startling oblique line in her magnolia-white skin--that skin so prized by Southern women and so carefully guarded with bonnets, veils and mittens against hot Georgia suns.

In the beginning of the novel, Rhett can be perceived as an impolite, direct, sly, naughty and sharp tongued character. However, as I read on towards the end, I discovered totally opposite of these descriptions. Rhett was in love with Scarlett from the very beginning. He is a courageous, caring, risk taker, compassionate, benevolent, generous, child loving man with a big kind heart. I started to adore and admire Rhett as a real man when I was about to finish the novel and I felt ache in my heart towards a person who dedicated his soul and his everything to win the heart of Scarlett, a well-respected business owner, a man who lost his favorite and only

child, a gentleman who regained the reverence of whole society and obtained nothing in return. Swarthy, muscular, tanned, hairy, interested in fashion, well-travelled, super well-educated even though he was kicked out of West Point, Rhett Butler is a bit of a romance novel wish fulfillment type. And he always seems steps ahead of everyone else. The evolution of his relationship with Scarlett is so carefully and artfully structured that the final 100 pages will fill your heart with sorrow.

Gerald O'hara, Scarlett's father, was sixty years old and his crisp curly hair was silver-white, but his shrewd face was unlined and his hard little blue eyes were young with the unworried youthfulness of one who has never taxed his brain with problems more abstract than how many cards to draw in a poker game. His was as Irish a face as could be found in the length and breadth of the homeland he had left so long ago round, high colored, short nosed, wide mouthed and belligerent. Beneath his choleric exterior Gerald O'Hara had the tenderest of hearts." He could not bear to see a slave pouting under a reprimand, no matter how well deserved, or hear a kitten mewling or a child crying; but he had a horror of having this weakness discovered. That everyone who met him did discover his kindly heart within five minutes was unknown to him; and his vanity would have suffered tremendously if he had found it out, for he liked to think that when he bawled orders at the top of his voice everyone trembled and obeyed.

Elen O'hara, Scarlett's mother, was thirty-two years old, and, according to the standards of her day, she was a middle-aged woman, one who had borne six children and buried three. She would have been a strikingly beautiful woman had there been any glow in her eyes, any responsive warmth in her smile or any spontaneity in her voice that fell with gentle melody on the ears of her family and her servants. She spoke in the soft slurring voice of the coastal Georgian, liquid of vowels, kind to consonants and with the barest trace of French accent. It was a voice never raised in command to a servant or reproof to a child but a voice that was obeyed instantly at Tara.

Mammy is one of the main characters as well. As Mitchell described, Mammy felt that she owned the O'Haras, body and soul, that their secrets were her secrets; and even a hint of a mystery was enough to set her upon the trail as relentlessly as a bloodhound. Scarlett knew from experience that, if Mammy's curiosity were not immediately satisfied, she would take up the matter with Ellen, and then Scarlett would be forced to reveal everything to her mother, or think up some plausible lie. She devoted to her last drop of blood to the O'Haras, Ellen's mainstay, the despair of her three daughters, the terror of the other house servants.

Mammy was black, but her code of conduct and her sense of pride were as high as or higher than those of her owners. She had been raised in the bedroom of Solange Robillard, Ellen O'Hara's mother, a dainty, cold, high-nosed Frenchwoman, who spared neither her children nor her servants their just punishment for any infringement of decorum. She had been Ellen's mammy and had come with her from Savannah to the up-country when she married.

I believe it's worth mentioning that *Gone with the Wind's* Southern sensibility is very solid. The South here is a living character all its own, and this brightness lends even deeper resonance to the story while breathing life into its large cast of characters. I know some have taken—and do take—issue with the Georgia of this era, when slavery and prejudice were very much a reality; however, it's always clear that Mitchell's goal was only authenticity and accuracy in portrayal, and she wasn't expressing personal sentiments. Told from the standpoint of the women left behind, author Margaret Mitchell brilliantly illustrates the heartbreaking and devastating effects of war on the land and its people.

Gone with the Wind is a brilliant book with vivid descriptions, rich source for language learners and I encourage anyone to read it. This novel really is one of those rare books that I will never forget.

References:

1. *Gone with the Wind* by Margaret Mitchell